

Polarographic Reduction of In(III)

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Polarographic reduction of In(III) at different pH, temperature and concentration of sodium perchlorate has been investigated. A reversible and diffusion controlled wave is obtained at $pH \geq 3$ having a half-wave potential of -0.512 volt vs SCE. At lower pH values the magnitude of limiting current decreases and the wave becomes irreversible and kinetic-controlled. In the pH range of 0.4 to 0.8 a minimum in the limiting current region is visible when potassium chloride salt-bridge is used. In presence of small amounts of potassium hydrogen phthalate the reduction of In(III) becomes reversible even at low pH values.

MANY contradictory results exist in the literature on reduction of In(III) in various complexing and non-complexing supporting electrolytes¹⁻²⁵. Irreversible reduction of In(III) has been observed in halides, nitrate and perchlorate media¹⁻⁷. On the other hand some workers have reported reversible reduction of In(III) in halides, thiocyanate and non-complexing media⁸⁻¹⁵. The reduction of In(III) has also been mentioned as quasi-reversible in certain supporting electrolytes¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

The values of half-wave potentials of In(III) reported by various workers also show considerable discrepancy. Some investigators¹⁹⁻²² were not even able to record the half-wave potentials due to the ill-defined nature of the wave, which was obtained by extrapolating the half wave potentials of In(III) in presence of varying concentrations of the ligand to zero ligand concentration.

The discrepancy observed by various workers in the nature of reduction and half-wave potential of In(III) prompted the authors to investigate the reduction of In(III) under different conditions. The polarographic reduction of In(III) has been systematically investigated at different pH, temperatures and concentrations of the supporting electrolyte (NaClO₄).

Experimental

Analytically pure grade reagents were used. Indium nitrate (Schuchardt, Munchen) was dissolved in dilute perchloric acid and was standardised against EDTA using PAN indicator²⁶. Sodium perchlorate obtained from Koch Lab., England was used as the supporting electrolyte. Potassium chloride and potassium hydrogen phthalate used were BDH products.

Measurements of current and half-wave potentials were made with OH-105 Radelkis polarograph and a manual Toshniwal polarograph in conjunction with a PYE galvanometer (Cambridge, England). The temperature of all the solutions was maintained constant at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, except otherwise stated, by immersing the cell and saturated calomel electrode

in an ultra thermostat. Measurements of pH were made on a NIG 333 digital pH meter. The pH of all the solutions was adjusted to the desired value by adding either dilute perchloric acid or CO₂-free sodium hydroxide solution.

The concentration of In(III) was kept at 2×10^{-4} M. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1 by adding NaClO₄, except at lower pH values where perchloric acid was used to adjust the pH. The polarographic cell was connected to the reference electrode through a sodium nitrate or potassium chloride salt-bridge.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH: Polarograms were recorded at different pH values. Two waves were obtained at low pH values in sodium perchlorate supporting electrolyte. At $pH > 3.0$ only one wave (first wave) was observed. With lowering of pH the limiting current of the first wave decreased while a second irreversible wave appeared. The half-wave potential of the second wave in presence of sodium nitrate salt bridge at pH values between 0.2 to 0.7 was -0.85 ± 0.02 volt vs SCE. Previous workers have also reported the existence of two waves of indium^{4,10,20}.

The values of current of the first wave at -0.6 volt vs SCE have been plotted against pH in Fig. 1. The plot shows that when sodium nitrate was used as salt bridge the current remained almost steady upto pH 1.0 ($\approx 0.16 \mu A$) and increased sharply at higher pH values. The maximum current ($2.27 \pm 0.03 \mu A$) was observed at $pH \approx 3.0$. The increase in current with increase of pH has been considered to be due to the formation of hydroxy complex $In(H_2O)_4(OH)_2$, which acts as a catalyst¹⁰. However, precipitation started at $pH > 3.4$, which appeared to be complete at $pH \approx 4.5$.

The waves obtained by recording polarograph at the same pH values are shown in Fig. 2. The wave become increasingly irreversible with decrease in pH of the solution. This observation was different from that of Lawson and Aikens¹⁰ who reported

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Fig. 1. Plot of current vs pH using sodium nitrate salt-bridge (O) and potassium chloride salt-bridge (●), for $2 \times 10^{-4} M$ In(III).

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on reduction of In(III) ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$) at 30° and $\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO_4). Salt-bridge—sodium nitrate.

reversible waves at low pH values. The wave appeared reversible only at $\text{pH} \geq 3$, wherein the plot of limiting current of In(III) vs its concentration or $\sqrt{h}$ (corrected height) gave a straight line passing through the origin. This indicated that the reduction at $\text{pH} \geq 3$ was diffusion controlled. The reversible half-wave potential was found to be -0.512 V vs SCE.

Effect of concentration of supporting electrolyte : When the polarograms were taken at pH 3.1, it was noticed that the half-wave potentials remained nearly constant upto the ionic strength of 0.8 (NaClO_4) (Table 1). However, the diffusion current decreased slightly with increase in ionic strength.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTE (NaClO_4) ON In(III) REDUCTION AT pH 3.1 AT 30°

In(III) = $2 \times 10^{-4} M$		
Ionic strength (μ)	Diffusion current (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (Volt)
0.1	2.30	0.512
0.2	2.30	0.512
0.3	2.23	0.512
0.5	2.22	0.512
0.8	2.16	0.511

Effect of temperature : The half-wave potentials and limiting currents recorded at different temperatures at pH 3 are reported in Table 2. The temperature coefficient of limiting current was calculated by using the relation :

$$\text{Temperature coefficient} = \frac{2.303}{T} \log \frac{T_2}{T_1}$$

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON In(III) REDUCTION AT pH 3.0

In(III) = $1.96 \times 10^{-4} M$		$\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO_4)
Temp. $^\circ C$	Limiting current (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (Volt)
15.0	1.78	0.530
25.0	2.10	0.518
30.0	2.20	0.512
37.5	2.30	0.502
49.0	2.73	0.495
54.0	2.91	0.488

The value of temperature coefficient from 15° to 54° has been found to be 0.0126, which comes to 1.26% per degree. The temperature coefficient value also suggested that the reduction wave was diffusion controlled. The temperature coefficient of the half-wave potential was ≈ 1.1 mV/degree.

Effect of KCl salt-bridge: Some investigators have reported abnormal behaviour of In (III) in presence of different concentrations of chloride ion^{6, 7, 9, 15, 19, 23, 24}. It was therefore decided to study the specific influence of potassium chloride salt-bridge. Usually the observations were taken keeping the potassium chloride salt-bridge in solution for about 15 to 20 minutes. In some cases

the polarograms were also recorded after placing the potassium chloride salt-bridge for longer periods.

The effect of potassium chloride salt-bridge is shown in Fig. 1. It can be observed that at low pH values the current was higher in presence of potassium chloride salt-bridge as compared to sodium nitrate salt-bridge. The current became nearly equal for both the salt-bridges at pH values between 2 and 3.

The current at low pH values did not remain constant when the readings were repeated at different intervals of time. Simultaneous readings have been taken at the same pH using sodium

Fig. 3. Effect of salt-bridge on reduction of In(III) ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$) at pH 0.7, temp. 30° and $\mu = 0.1(\text{NaClO}_4)$. ((A)—potassium chloride salt-bridge and (B)—sodium nitrate salt-bridge.

nitrate salt-bridge and potassium chloride salt-bridge. The Fig. 3 shows that at pH 0.7 the shapes of the waves are altogether different for the two salt-bridges. In presence of potassium chloride salt-bridge height of the first wave was considerably high with a faint minimum at nearly -0.6 to -0.8 V. The remarkable influence of potassium chloride salt-bridge may be due to leakage of traces of potassium chloride into the test solution.

The reduction behaviour of In(III) in presence of potassium chloride salt-bridge at different pH values is presented in Table 3. The results show that the potassium chloride salt-bridge has significant effect at low pH values. The half-wave potential observed at $\text{pH} \geq 3$ with potassium chloride salt-bridge was slightly higher compared to that obtained with sodium nitrate salt-bridge.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF POTASSIUM CHLORIDE SALT-BRIDGE ON HALF-WAVE POTENTIAL AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

pH	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}^*$ (Volt)	Remarks
2.0 M Perchloric acid	0.95 (Second wave)	Only second irreversible wave was observed
0.45	0.516	Irreversible with minimum
0.80	0.91 (Second wave)	
1.00	0.527	Irreversible with minimum
1.50	0.527	
2.02	0.543	Irreversible, minimum was absent
2.50	0.560	Irreversible
3.00	0.521	"
3.20	0.516	Reversible
	0.517	Reversible

*Half-wave potential of first wave except otherwise stated.

Kinetic character of the waves: The ratios of the current at 58.5 cm (corrected) and 18.5 cm (corrected) of mercury height using sodium nitrate salt-bridge and potassium chloride salt-bridge have been given in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. The ratio is nearly equal to the theoretical value (1.78) at pH 3.0-3.3 but decreases on lowering the pH in both the cases. It was only 1.05 at pH 0.9 in the case of sodium nitrate salt-bridge indicating that the wave became kinetic-controlled at pH 0.9. However, the wave was partially kinetic-controlled at the same pH value when potassium chloride salt-bridge was used.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF pH ON THE RATIO OF In(III) LIMITING CURRENTS AT 58.5 AND 18.5 cm MERCURY COLUMN AT 30°; $\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO₄)

pH Ratio	Salt-bridge—Sodium nitrate				
	0.90	1.10	1.50	2.60	3.10
	1.05	1.14	1.52	1.65	1.78
					1.77

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF pH ON THE RATIO OF In(III) LIMITING CURRENTS AT 58.5 AND 18.5 cm MERCURY COLUMN AT 30° AND $\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO₄)

pH Ratio	Salt-bridge—Potassium chloride				
	0.80	0.90	1.50	2.50	3.10
	1.58	1.61	1.65	1.67	1.79
					1.78

Role of potassium hydrogen phthalate: The effect of pH on the reduction of In(III) in the presence of phthalate is presented in the Table 6. These results show that the reduction of In(III) becomes reversible even at low pH values on addition of phthalate. The amount of phthalate required to make the wave reversible decreased on increasing the pH. The half-wave potential increased slightly on increasing the pH, but it remained nearly constant (-0.512 V) in the pH range 2.8-3.2. The wave was found to be diffusion controlled at pH 2.9-3.3.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF POTASSIUM HYDROGEN PHTHALATE ON In(III) REDUCTION AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

pH	Phthalate $M \times 10^6$	i_l (μA)	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ Volt	Slope Volt
1.70	10	2.02 (1.09)	0.509	0.0225
2.44	5	2.17 (1.84)	0.510	0.0220
2.80	3	2.20 (2.04)	0.511	0.0215
3.02	3	2.23 (2.23)	0.512	0.0200
3.20	3	2.29 (2.29)	0.512	0.0210

Figures in parenthesis are of corresponding limiting current in the absence of phthalate.

Strizhov *et al*^{27,28} have reported that phthalate acts as a catalyst in the reduction of In(III). It seems that the effect of phthalate in the present case may be due to the preferential adsorption of indium phthalate complex on the mercury drop, facilitating the reduction of In(III). Phthalate thus acts as a catalyst.

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